

Mathematical Equivalence of the Real Wave Quantum Mechanics Algorithm with Schrödinger's Equation

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April 14, 2026

Abstract

It has been shown elsewhere [1], without theoretical justification, that in 1-dimension the Real Wave Quantum Mechanics algorithm can be 'tuned' to give the same solutions as the Schrödinger equation. This paper provides a theoretical justification for this result and identifies the origin of the tuning parameters. An illustrative example based on the Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential is provided.

Keywords: Real Wave Quantum Mechanics, Quantum ontology, Schrödinger's equation, Second spatial derivative, Origin of α , Numerical algorithms, Madelung constant

1 Introduction

In 'The Distributed Electron'[1] a candidate hidden variables theory of the electron was developed. Called Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM), the theory is based on a grid of cells with unit size equal to the Compton wavelength of the electron, within each of which there is a vortex in an underlying massive ether. For convenience the cells have been called Field Rotators (FRs). Upon assuming:

- that the FRs gain in amplitude by resonance with oscillations in the ether (vacuum) field whose intensity is controlled by the local potential (numerically equivalent to the Coulomb potential but not interpreted in terms of electrostatics)

- that the cells interact by absorbing and re-radiating a fraction, α , of the wave energy of which they are formed,

solutions can be obtained using matrix eigenvalue methods. The solutions are 'structures' which closely resemble the form of solutions of the Schrödinger equation but which additionally provide insights into other quantum features such as spin and the Pauli Exclusion principle. A key feature of the structures is that the phase of adjacent FRs alternates (changes by π radians), a situation which hereafter is referred to as 'Phase Alternation' (PA).

Physical electron structures are 3-dimensional and interactions between every FR (including their relative phases) must be considered. Restricting application to 1-D restricts the phase variation to \pm i.e all contributions to the final sum are real. Nevertheless, it is informative to apply the model in this way and it has been shown [1], without theoretical justification, that numerically exact solutions of Schrödinger equation arise from tuning of the parameters. The present paper provides the theoretical justification for this result and identifies the specific conditions which lead to it.

In Section 2, a mathematical relationship between the RWQM algorithm and the second derivative of a wavefunction is identified empirically and a theoretical basis for it is developed. There is no physical content in this. In Section 2.2, we move towards the physical interpretation by allowing the interaction coefficient α between FRs to be other than one. Assuming continuity at FRs (gains balance losses) we are able to develop a differential equation for RWQM in the same form as Schrödinger's equation. Comparing the two equations allows the value of α which leads to exact replication of Schrödinger results to be found. In Section 2.3 these findings are verified by applying them to the 1-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential. Exact numerical agreement is demonstrated. Finally, in Section 3 we discuss the relevance of the findings to the physical RWQM distributed electron..

2 The RWQM Algorithm and the Second Derivative in 1-Dimension

First we will demonstrate that the RWQM algorithm is mathematically related to the second spatial derivative. In this context the algorithm is devoid of physical content and is applied as follows:

Figure 1: Comparison theoretical 2nd Differential with PA method

x	Theoretical	AHS	% AHS error	Finite Diff	% FD error
-750	-0.385557	-0.385412	-0.037733	-0.385583	0.006610
-584	-20.034000	-20.0337	-0.001354	-20.0344	0.002022
-418	-97.128100	-97.1292	0.001116	-97.1259	-0.002313
-252	281.294000	281.297	0.000985	281.289	-0.001956
-86	-223.691000	-223.695	0.001992	-223.682	-0.003991
80	231.532000	231.537	0.001996	231.523	-0.003998
246	-288.906000	-288.909	0.001040	-288.9	-0.002067
412	94.695200	94.6964	0.001235	94.6928	-0.002553
578	22.276300	22.276	-0.001238	22.2767	0.001872
744	0.458987	0.458843	-0.031327	0.459016	0.006427

Table 1: Comparing theoretical 2nd differential with that calculated using Alternating Harmonic Series (AHS) and 2nd order central finite difference methods

- Assume that we have a well behaved normalizable function, $f(x)$, which we are able to evaluate at regular points. (For example, it could be derived from data by interpolation.)
- Select a suitably small finite difference, Δx , as would be done in normal finite difference calculations.
- Construct a 'kernel', F , of weights based on the two-sided negated alternating harmonic series (AHS). For example, the contribution from a neighbouring point would be $-1 \times$ the value of the function at that point, the next one contributes $1/2 \times$ its value, the next but one $-1/3$ and so on.
- Convolve the kernel with the values of the function across the whole range of discrete x values separated by Δx . The total contribution found by the convolution at x_i is $F * \psi$ where the asterisk denotes the convolution process.

Applying this procedure to a sample wavefunction we find that the 2nd spatial derivative at x_i is given empirically by:

$$\frac{d^2\psi_i}{dx^2} = 8 \ln 2 \left(\frac{-F * \psi}{2 \ln 2} - f(x_i) \right) \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \quad (1)$$

This is illustrated in Figure 1 and Table 1, which compare the theoretical value of $d^2\psi/dx^2$ for a normalizable trial function (calculated symbolically using Sympy) with the results using the above equation. For comparison, the table also includes the results using the standard 2nd order central finite difference expression. The error is $< 0.002\%$ for AHS: the algorithm is roughly twice as accurate as the finite difference method. We would like to understand how this relationship arises.

2.1 Mathematical Analysis

Before we consider any implications for Schrödinger's equation we demonstrate the theoretical basis for Equation 1. To perform the analysis we will proceed as follows:

- Using a suitably small increment Δx , develop the Taylor series expansion about some point ψ_0 to enable magnitudes of adjacent points to be estimated in terms of differentials at ψ_0 .

Table 2: Taylor expansions

Term	ψ_{-3}	ψ_{-2}	ψ_{-1}	ψ_0	ψ_1	ψ_2	ψ_3
$f(x)$	ψ_0	ψ_0	ψ_0	ψ_0	ψ_0	ψ_0	ψ_0
$f'(x) = \beta$	$-3\Delta x\beta$	$-2\Delta x\beta$	$-\Delta x\beta$	0	$\Delta x\beta$	$2\Delta x\beta$	$3\Delta x\beta$
$f''(x) = \gamma$	$\frac{9}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{4}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	0	$\frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{4}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{9}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$
$f'''(x) = \delta$	$-\frac{27}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$-\frac{8}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$-\frac{1}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	0	$\frac{1}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$\frac{8}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$\frac{27}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$

- Apply the alternating harmonic kernel (essentially the RWQM algorithm in 1 dimension) to the calculated Taylor values and calculate the contribution at ψ_0 .
- Ascertain what value of the second differential is required to match the contributions to the actual value ψ_0 .

The Taylor expansions for $f(x+h)$ and $f(x-h)$ where $h > 0$ are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(x+h) &= f(x) + hf' + \frac{1}{2!}h^2f'' + \frac{1}{3!}h^3f''' + \dots \\
 f(x-h) &= f(x) - hf' + \frac{1}{2!}h^2f'' - \frac{1}{3!}h^3f''' + \dots
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

Let us set $h = \Delta x$ as the discretization step size.¹

In Table 2 we calculate the first 4 terms of the expansion for a central point and six neighbouring points. Note that for clarity we have written the first, second and third derivatives as β, γ, δ respectively in the table. We now apply the convolution kernel of Eq 3 to calculate $\tilde{\psi}_0$

$$\dots \frac{1}{4} \quad -\frac{1}{3} \quad +\frac{1}{2} \quad -1 \quad 0 \quad -1 \quad +\frac{1}{2} \quad -\frac{1}{3} \quad +\frac{1}{4} \dots
 \tag{3}$$

The results are given in Table 3 . The result of the discrimination process for $\tilde{\psi}_0$ is the sum of all the written terms plus those extending to infinity in

¹In the application of RWQM to physical situations we will be setting this distance to the Compton wavelength of the electron which is small compared to typical electron wavestructures.

Table 3: Discriminate to find contributions to $\tilde{\psi}_0$. Achieved by Alternating signs (i.e. phase) and dividing by distance.

Term	ψ_{-3}	ψ_{-2}	ψ_{-1}	ψ_0	ψ_1	ψ_2	ψ_3
$f(x)$	$-\psi_0/3$	$\psi_0/2$	$-\psi_0$	$\tilde{\psi}_0$	$-\psi_0$	$\psi_0/2$	$-\psi_0/3$
$f'(x) = \beta$	$3\Delta x\beta/3$	$-2\Delta x\beta/2$	$\Delta x\beta$	0	$-\Delta x\beta$	$2\Delta x\beta/2$	$-3\Delta x\beta/3$
$f''(x) = \gamma$	$-\frac{9}{2 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{4}{2 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$-\frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	0	$-\frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$\frac{4}{2 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$	$-\frac{9}{2 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^2\gamma$
$f'''(x) = \delta$	$\frac{27}{6 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$-\frac{8}{6 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$\frac{1}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	0	$-\frac{1}{6}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$\frac{8}{6 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^3\delta$	$-\frac{27}{6 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^3\delta$

either direction. Consider first the $f(x)$ row:

$$\dots - \psi_0/3 + \psi_0/2 - \psi_0 - \psi_0 + \psi_0/2 - \psi_0/3\dots \quad (4)$$

Factoring out $-2\psi_0$ gives:

$$-2\psi_0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \dots \right) \quad (5)$$

and we recognise the bracketed terms as the alternating harmonic series, which is known to converge to $\ln 2$. Hence the first row sums to $-2\psi_0 \ln 2$.² Examination of the terms in row 2 shows that they sum to zero, as do the terms in row 4. To evaluate row 3 (the second differential row) we proceed as follows:

$$-\frac{9}{2 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^2\gamma + \frac{4}{2 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma - \frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma - \frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma + \frac{4}{2 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma - \frac{9}{2 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^2\gamma \quad (6)$$

First recognise that the terms can be paired so the sum becomes:

$$2 \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma + \frac{4}{2 \cdot 2}(\Delta x)^2\gamma - \frac{9}{2 \cdot 3}(\Delta x)^2\gamma \dots \right) \quad (7)$$

²We note that with $\psi_0 = 1$, this is Madelung's [2],[3] first (1-D) constant from crystallography which describes the net electrostatic field at an ion in a linear crystal having alternating positive and negative charges. Because we have restricted consideration to 1-D the analysis is identical.

Factoring out $-(\Delta x)^2\gamma/2$ and cancelling where possible gives:

$$-(\Delta x)^2\gamma(1 - 2 + 3.....) \quad (8)$$

Let the bracketed sum be S and introduce Grandi's series G :

$$G = 1 - 1 + 1 - 1.... \quad (9)$$

By analytic continuation it can be shown that this 'sums' to $1/2$.³ Now consider $S - G$:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= +1 & -2 & +3 & -4... \\ -G &= -1 & +1 & -1 & +1... \\ S - G &= +0 & -1 & +2 & -3... \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

From this it is clear that $S - G = -S$ or using the known value of $G = 1/2$:

$$S = \frac{1}{4} \quad (11)$$

The infinity of contributions has been subsumed into a convergent series representation. Substituting this value in Eq. 8 gives the third row sum $-(\Delta x)^2\gamma/4$ and the total sum of the discrimination process is:

$$-2\psi_0 \ln 2 - (\Delta x)^2\gamma/4 \quad (12)$$

To check that this conforms to the posited Eq. 1:

$$\frac{d^2\psi_i}{dx^2} = 8 \ln 2 \left(\frac{-F * \psi}{2 \ln 2} - f(x_i) \right) \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^2}$$

we can substitute for $-F * \psi$, remembering that we have been using γ to denote the second derivative. Also note that ψ_i in Eq. 1 is the same thing as ψ_0 in the Taylor analysis i.e. the value of ψ at the point of interest.

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= 8 \ln 2 \left(\frac{-(-2\psi_0 \ln 2 - (\Delta x)^2\gamma/4)}{2 \ln 2} - \psi_0 \right) \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^2} \\ \gamma &= 8 \ln 2 \left(\psi_0 + \frac{(\Delta x)^2\gamma}{8 \ln 2} - \psi_0 \right) \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^2} \\ \gamma &= \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

This confirms that Eq. 1 can be used to estimate the second differential of a function.

³This result has been the subject of considerable discussion in the public arena. We will proceed to use it because we will show that it leads to the correct results!

2.2 The link between RWQM and Schrödinger's equation

After this mathematical detour we can examine its link to RWQM and the Schrödinger equation. First we note that Table 3 is based on 'full interaction' between the FRs i.e. we have used $1/distance$ in calculating contributions. In RWQM we do not expect full interaction: rather we assume some small fraction α of the waves forming an FR is absorbed and re-radiated and that this fraction is a fundamental feature of nature. Discrimination should therefore be based on $\alpha/distance$. As α is a linear factor in every term of Table 3 we can factor it out in Eq 12 to give the total discriminated contributions:

$$-\alpha (2\psi \ln 2 + (\Delta x)^2 \gamma / 4) \quad (14)$$

or substituting back for γ :

$$-\alpha \left(2\psi \ln 2 + (\Delta x)^2 \frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} \right) \quad (15)$$

Δx is the standard unit of distance in RWQM, so we can make the second bracketed term specifically dimensionless by converting from x , which has units of length, to z which is the dimensionless distance. Doing so cancels out the $(\Delta x)^2$ term, giving:

$$-\alpha \left(2\psi \ln 2 + \frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2 \psi}{dz^2} \right) \quad (16)$$

The interaction term is negative - contributions from other FRs interfere destructively to reduce the amplitude at each FR by the amount shown. In any steady state structure these losses must be balanced by gains, and in RWQM we have posited that such gains arise from resonance with the local vacuum field:

$$gains = (V_v + V(x) - E) \psi \quad (17)$$

Specifically, we assume that

- within free space there is some constant intensity of the electron Compton frequency vacuum field, V_v .⁴

⁴We do not consider it to be a universal constant, and specifically anticipate that it will be a function of the gravitational field.

- there will be some variation in the available resonance gain arising from the local presence of other structures. Given the success of Quantum Mechanics using the Coulomb potential, it seems reasonable to assume its mathematical form, but without reference to electrostatics, which is viewed as non-fundamental at this level. ⁵

For a steady state we expect the gains and losses to balance at each FR i.e. we wish to put:

$$\text{gains} + \text{losses} = 0$$

To perform this comparison we must first render the gains equation in dimensionless form which is achieved by dividing through by the electron rest mass energy content $E_e \equiv m_e c^2$ Now balancing gains and losses leads to a differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
-\alpha \left(2\psi \ln 2 + \frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} \right) + (V_v/E_e + V(x)/E_e - E_s/E_e) \psi &= 0 \\
-2\psi \ln 2 - \frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} &= \frac{1}{\alpha} (E_s/E_e - V_v/E_e - V(x)/E_e) \psi = 0 \\
-\frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} &= \frac{1}{\alpha} (E_s/E_e - V_v/E_e - V(x)/E_e) \psi + 2\psi \ln 2 \\
-\frac{1}{4} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} &= \frac{1}{\alpha} (E_s/E_e - V_v/E_e - V(x)/E_e + 2\alpha \ln 2) \psi \\
-\frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} &= \frac{4}{\alpha} (E_s/E_e - V_v/E_e - V(x)/E_e + 2\alpha \ln 2) \psi \\
-\frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + \frac{4}{\alpha} (V(x)/E_e - E_s/E_e + V_v/E_e - 2\alpha \ln 2) \psi &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Let

$$\epsilon = \frac{E_s}{E_e}; \quad W = \frac{V(z)}{E_e}$$

be the dimensionless energies:

$$-\frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + \frac{4}{\alpha} (W - \epsilon + V_v/E_e - 2\alpha \ln 2) \psi = 0 \tag{19}$$

We would like to compare this with the time-independent Schrödinger equation:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + (V(x) - E) = 0 \tag{20}$$

⁵For us, electrostatics is a property which emerges when considering the interactions of many fundamental structures.

To make direct comparison we must first express Schrödinger's equation in dimensionless form using the standard RWQM values for length and energy. Substituting $z = x/L$ into equation 20 and noting we must now use $V(z)$ we get:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + L^2 (V(z) - E_s) \psi = 0 \quad (21)$$

Divide through by E_e and again using

$$\epsilon = \frac{E_s}{E_e}; \quad W = \frac{V(z)}{E_e}$$

:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2E_e m_e} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + L^2 (W - \epsilon) \psi = 0 \quad (22)$$

Substituting the RWQM values for length and energy, namely:

$$L = \lambda_c = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{m_e c}; \quad E_e = m_e c^2$$

gives:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e m_e c^2} \frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + \frac{(2\pi\hbar)^2}{(m_e c)^2} (W - \epsilon) \psi = 0 \quad (23)$$

Simplifying:

$$-\frac{d^2\psi}{dz^2} + 8\pi^2 (W - \epsilon) \psi = 0 \quad (24)$$

This is the form needed for direct comparison with the RWQM equation 19. Equivalence requires that:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2\pi^2} \quad (25)$$

and

$$V_v - \frac{2E_e \ln 2}{2\pi^2} = 0 \quad (26)$$

i.e. the dimensionless form of V_v is:

$$\frac{V_v}{E_e} = \frac{\ln 2}{\pi^2} \quad (27)$$

2.3 Illustrative Example

As a check, we can compare results for the 1D Simple Harmonic Oscillator potential (SHO):

- calculated using the discretized Schrödinger equation
- calculated using the RWQM algorithm with the determined values for α and V_v .⁶

Schrödinger's equation can be discretized for numerical solution using the finite difference approximation for the second derivative:

$$\frac{d^2\psi_i}{dz^2} \approx \frac{\psi_{i+1} - 2\psi_i + \psi_{i-1}}{(\Delta z)^2}$$

Re-arranging gives:

$$\frac{\psi_{i+1}}{8\pi^2} + \psi_i \left(\frac{1}{4\pi^2} + W_i \right) - \frac{\psi_{i-1}}{8\pi^2} = \epsilon\psi_i \quad (28)$$

which readily converts to a tridiagonal matrix form and can be solved using standard eigenvalue computations in Scipy. The RWQM approach uses a similar matrix eigenvalue calculation, except that the matrix is not sparse, since interactions between every FR are calculated.

Performing the SHO comparison for a spring constant of 5×10^{-10} gives the results shown in Figure 2. Results from the two different methods are practically identical.

3 Discussion

There is no such thing as a 1-dimensional electron so it would be wrong to read too much physical importance into these findings, which are essentially mathematical. We have pinpointed that under specific conditions, namely $\alpha = \frac{1}{2\pi^2}$ and $\frac{V_v}{E_e} = \frac{\ln 2}{\pi^2}$, the 1-d RWQM and Schrödinger equations are equivalent - they have the same solutions. From a physical perspective this result is curious. Underlying the motivation for RWQM is the assumption that FRs

⁶Similar results were presented in [1]. These were arrived at by adjusting parameters to illustrate that agreement was possible, without any theoretical basis.

Figure 2: Comparing results for Schrodinger and RWQM methods with $C = 5e - 10$. The RWQM results are calculated with $\alpha = 1/(2\pi^2)$. V_v is found by ensuring the ratios between the first and second energies is 1:3. The required value is $\ln 2/\pi^2$ as identified by the theory. The plots are practically identical despite being produced by the different methods in separate programs.

re-emit some fraction of the wave energy forming them as spiral waves. We have no idea what that fraction would be but it would certainly result from a complicated non-linear process. It would seem to be hugely coincidental if it turned out to be exactly $\frac{1}{2\pi^2}$. However, there is another physical factor involved in the Schrödinger equation: the electron mass m_e , which is equivalent to the frequency ($E = mc^2 = \hbar\omega$) which in turn fixes the Compton wavelength and hence the size of the unit RWQM cells. The discriminated wave energy arriving at an FR depends on the re-radiation fraction, but also independently on the distance the waves have travelled i.e. the cell size. Speculating, is it possible that the mass of the electron is such that it reconciles the physical re-radiation coefficient with the mathematical requirements we have described?

It is clear that we should seek to apply a similar analysis to higher dimensions. In doing so we will depart from the simple Madelung-like analysis of 1-d because the phase of waves arriving from different directions must be taken into account. We have already shown in [1] that RWQM gives stable eigenstructures in 2 and 3 dimensions but without establishing the exact relationship to Schrödinger's equation, as we have been able to do here in 1 dimension.

References

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